

STABILITY ASSESSMENT OF THE TORANICA TAILINGS DAM

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ABSTRACT. This study presents a comprehensive analysis and assessment of the structural stability and functional performance of the *Toranica* tailings dam near the town of Kriva palanka, North Macedonia, based on monitoring data from 2022. The dam complex includes upstream and downstream embankments, a settling lake, drainage systems, and auxiliary infrastructure. Regular technical inspections, piezometric monitoring, hydrological measurements, and numerical modelling were conducted to evaluate filtration, stress-strain behaviour, and safety factors. Results confirm that the dam structures operated within safety parameters, with no critical deformations or filtration anomalies observed. Stability modelling validated the geotechnical reliability of both embankments, supporting continued safe operation and further vertical expansion. Recommendations for future monitoring and maintenance are proposed to ensure long-term structural integrity and environmental compliance.

Key words: hydro-tailings pond, geophysics, electrical resistivity tomography (ERT).

АНАЛИЗ И ОЦЕНКА НА СТАБИЛНОСТТА НА ХВОСТОХРАНИЛИЩЕ „ТОРАНИЦА“

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Това проучване представя цялостен анализ и оценка на структурната стабилност и функционалните характеристики на хвостохранилището „Тораница“ близо до Крива паланка, Република Северна Македония, въз основа на данни от мониторинг от 2022 г. Комплексът от язовирната стена включва горни и долни насипи, утайтелно езеро, дренажни системи и спомагателна инфраструктура. Провеждани са редовни технически инспекции, пиезометричен мониторинг, хидрологични измервания и числено моделиране за оценка на филтрацията, поведението на напрежение-деформация и коефициентите на безопасност. Резултатите потвърждават, че язовирните конструкции са функционирали в рамките на параметрите за безопасност, без наблюдавани критични деформации или аномалии във филтрацията. Моделирането на стабилността е потвърдило геотехническата надеждност на двата насипа, поддържайки продължаващата безопасна експлоатация и по-нататъшното вертикално разширение. Предлагат се препоръки за бъдещ мониторинг и поддръжка, за да се гарантира дългосрочна структурна цялост и екологично съответствие.

Ключови думи: хвостохранилище, геофизика, електротомография.

Introduction

Tailings dams are critical infrastructure units in mining operations, designed to safely contain the fine-grained waste (tailings) generated during mineral processing (Aleksandrova and Kopriv, 2020). These engineered embankments not only support the ongoing production activities of a mine, but also play a vital role in environmental protection by preventing the release of potentially harmful materials into the surrounding ecosystem. As stated by Tomova (2023), mineral processing is mainly focused on extracting the most valuable components from the ore, while the rest of the material is disposed of at the tailings ponds. Their importance has grown in the context of increasing mining volumes, stricter environmental regulations, and the global push toward sustainable development.

In modern mining practice, the safe and responsible management of tailings is essential to achieving the principles of sustainable development – meeting present economic and social needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. This involves minimising the ecological footprint of mining activities, ensuring the structural integrity of waste containment facilities, and maintaining public and environmental safety.

As Grigorova and Nishkov (2014) stated in recent years, the scale of mining operations has expanded significantly due to advancements in technologies related to drilling, hauling, bulk material handling, crushing, and mineral processing. These improvements have enabled higher production rates and the economic extraction of lower-grade ores, but they have also led to a dramatic increase in the volume of mine waste, particularly tailings. As a result, modern tailings management now faces the dual challenge of safely handling growing quantities of waste while minimising long-term environmental risks.

According to Tomova (2023), the management of mine waste is a complex and multifaceted task. Ensuring the safe and efficient disposal of extractive waste materials poses both technical and environmental difficulties. Numerous studies emphasise that mining and ore processing activities produce substantial quantities of waste, which require proper handling to minimise environmental hazards. Among the various sources of risk in mining operations, tailings ponds represent one of the most critical. As such, the selection of suitable methods for tailings discharge and dam construction is essential for the effective operation of these facilities (Tayebi-Khorami et al., 2019; Yankova, 2020). The operational sequence for constructing and raising combined mine waste facilities must be carefully planned and executed to ensure long-term safety and performance (Aleksandrova et al., 2021).

The *Toranica* Mine in North Macedonia, which processes lead-zinc ores through flotation, produces a significant volume of tailings – approximately 90% of the ore mass – mixed with flotation reagents (Petrov et al., 2024).

The *Toranitsa* tailings pond, with the tailings dam and the tailings lake, are in the immediate vicinity of the town of Kriva Palanka, at an approximate distance of 15 km, and were formed for the needs of the *Toranitsa* mine.

The location of the tailings dump is 4 km away downstream of the flotation factory in the Kriva Reka valley, between the "Varoshani" and the "Tsepen Kamen", which is located immediately after the confluence of the Toranichka River in the Kriva Reka River.

Fig. 1. Location of the *Toranisa* hydro-reservoir (closed red polygon)

The proper disposal of this material is vital for both environmental and operational reasons. The *Toranica* tailings dam, located near the town of Kriva Palanka, serves a dual purpose:

- secure storage of flotation tailings;
- clarification of process water before it is released into the natural water system.

This paper presents an integrated analysis of the stability and functionality of the *Toranica* tailings dam system based on monitoring data from 2022. The study aims to verify the dam's structural integrity, evaluate its performance under current operational conditions, and propose recommendations for its continued safe use in line with sustainable mining practices.

Site description - location and general layout

The *Toranica* tailings dam complex is situated approximately 15 km east of Kriva Palanka in northeastern North Macedonia. It lies in a narrow valley formed by the Kriva and the Toranica Rivers and was constructed to serve the operational needs of the nearby *Toranica* lead-zinc mine. The tailings facility consists of a system of interconnected structures forming a canyon-type accumulation basin that supports both tailings deposition and water management. (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Satellite image of the *Toranica* tailings pond

The hydrotechnical complex includes the following major elements:

- Upstream retention dam (retention embankment): built with a clay core and local materials, with gradual height increases using cycloned tailings sand.
- Downstream sand dam: formed by sequentially depositing cycloned sand fractions, reinforced with geosynthetic materials and drainage systems.
- Tailings lake (settling basin): formed between the two dams, it enables sedimentation of fine tailings and allows for water clarification.
- Diversion tunnel: redirects the natural flow of the Kriva River to prevent inflow into the tailings facility during floods.
- Overflow collector system: removes clarified water from the lake through a network of predesigned outlet structures.
- Pulp pipeline: a gravity-fed PVC pipeline that transports tailings slurry from the flotation plant to the dam, equipped with pressure-reduction chambers

The *Toranica* tailings dam is designed with dual functionality:

1. Storage of tailings produced during flotation of lead-zinc ore.
2. Retention and treatment of water used in the process, allowing for sedimentation of fine particles and controlled release of clean water into the environment.

The design follows a progressive construction concept, where both the upstream and downstream dams are raised in parallel over time to increase the storage capacity as needed. The separation of sand and fine fractions via hydrocyclones enables efficient material use: sand is used to build the dam, while fine material settles in the lake.

Fig. 3. Part of old and new collector and precipitators

This modular and adaptive design, combined with systematic monitoring and environmental control, supports the long-term sustainability and safety of the *Toranica* mine's tailings disposal operations.

Geological and geotechnical setting

The stability of tailings dam structures is heavily influenced by the geological and hydrogeological characteristics of the foundation terrain. A comprehensive understanding of the subsurface conditions at the *Toranica* tailings facility is essential for assessing both the structural integrity and long-term performance of the dam complex. The importance of creating reliable 3D geological models for slope stability assessment in similar mining contexts has been demonstrated by Alexandrova

(2018), who applied such modelling to the *Mizia* quarry, highlighting the role of geological heterogeneity in determining slope behaviour.

The *Toranica* tailings dam is located in a narrow valley formed by the *Kriva* and the *Toranica* Rivers, underlain by a diverse geological sequence comprising both unconsolidated and crystalline bedrock materials. The area exhibits a combination of alluvial and proluvial deposits (gravels, sands, and blocks) along the riverbeds, as well as metamorphic rocks, primarily albite-quartz-chlorite schists and gneisses, in the valley flanks and foundation zones.

These crystalline rocks, common in the region of "Cepen Kamen," are categorised as medium to weakly fractured and partially weathered, with varying degrees of tectonic deformation. The alluvial sediments in the river valleys represent relatively young and unconsolidated deposits, often forming the immediate substrate beneath the embankments.

Engineering-geological characteristics

Upstream dam zone

The upstream (retention) dam is founded partly on albitised schists and gneisses, and partly on thick alluvial-proluvial cover. These materials demonstrate variable geomechanical properties:

- The albite-quartz-chlorite schists are fine-grained, grey-green rocks with schistosity and common open fractures. These fractures allow limited groundwater circulation, classifying the rock as a relative hydrogeological collector in fractured zones.
- The gneisses are more massive and coherent, showing moderate strength and low permeability outside faulted zones.

According to the GN-200 geotechnical classification, these rocks fall into Category V, indicating moderately stable conditions suitable for dam foundation with appropriate engineering measures.

Fig. 4. Upstream dam zone

The alluvial-proluvial sediments – gravelly-sandy with frequent large clasts – are generally highly permeable ($k_f = 10^{-3}$ to 10^{-5} cm/s) and serve as unconfined aquifers in places. Their thickness ranges from 15 to 34 metres, with shallow groundwater levels between 0.8 and 1.9 metres.

Downstream dam zone

The downstream (sand) dam also rests on similar alluvial and crystalline materials. The geotechnical characteristics are consistent with those observed in the upstream area, but here, the hydraulic conductivity and strength of the sandy deposits are more critical due to the dam being constructed entirely of tailings-derived sand. These sands are deposited hydraulically and compacted by natural sedimentation.

To improve geotechnical performance, a drainage system with geotextiles, geomembranes, and graded filters was installed in the downstream toe area. This design helps manage seepage and enhances slope stability.

The hydrogeological regime of the area is influenced by:

- Surface water from the *Kriva* and the *Toranica* Rivers, which is diverted via a dedicated tunnel to prevent direct inflow into the tailings pond.
- Shallow groundwater in alluvial sediments, with locally high water tables.
- Seepage from the tailings pond, monitored through piezometers placed within and around both dams.

Fig. 5. Downstream (sand) dam

The permeability of the underlying materials varies significantly. While fractured crystalline rocks and coarse alluvial layers allow groundwater flow, the presence of a clay core and engineered filters in the dams helps control seepage paths and reduces uplift pressures.

Objectives and scope of monitoring

The monitoring program at the *Toranica* site is intended to:

- Ensure the structural stability of the upstream and downstream dams.
- Control and analyse the pore water pressures within the embankments.
- Track the water level fluctuations in the settling pond (tailings lake).
- Evaluate the performance of drainage and overflow systems.
- Detect possible deformations or displacements in the dam body or foundation.
- Verify compliance with regulatory and design safety requirements.

To complete this task, the following techniques are applied regularly:

- **Piezometric monitoring.** A network of 20 piezometers is installed across the upstream and downstream embankments, providing data on groundwater levels and pore water pressures. The piezometers are strategically placed to cover different zones - 6 piezometers within the upstream (retention) dam and 14 piezometers in the downstream (sand) dam. Data from the piezometric network in both the upstream and downstream dams demonstrated consistent and predictable pore water pressure behaviour. Random piezometer readings from downstream dam are shown on Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Water level in piezometers P-2, P-11, P-13, and P-15, water level in a sedimentary lake (TE), and elevation of the crown of a downstream dam (Kkr) for the year 2022.

Piezometers in the downstream dam showed low and stable water tables, well below the dam crest, confirming the efficiency of the drainage system.

Piezometers in the upstream dam also indicated controlled phreatic levels, especially in areas reinforced with geotextiles and geocomposites.

- **Surface water level monitoring.** The water level in the tailings pond is measured at least four times per month.
- **Flow rate measurements.** Discharge from the overflow collector and drainage outlets is monitored to track seepage and surface water outflows. Measurements help identify anomalies, such as increased seepage or blockages in the drainage systems.
- **Visual inspections.** Visual inspections are performed monthly and after major rainfall events. Observations are documented in technical reports and supplemented by photographic records.
- **Geodetic surveys.** Benchmark points are installed on both dams for detecting potential displacements. Geodetic measurements are taken periodically to verify that the embankments remain stable and that no differential settlement is occurring.
- **Water quality control.** Water samples from the tailings pond, drainage discharges, and monitoring wells are analysed for physical and chemical parameters. This ensures that water released into the Kriva Reka River complies with environmental standards and that no contamination from flotation reagents is occurring.

The factors of safety calculated from numerical models further support the assessment that both embankments maintain a high degree of stability under static conditions.

This is especially important given the method of dam construction, which relies on cycloned tailings sand — a material whose geotechnical properties can vary over time. The effectiveness of the drainage system, including geotextiles, geomembranes, and granular filters, plays a key role in maintaining slope stability and preventing excess pore pressures that could lead to failure.

The integrated monitoring system at *Toranica* has proven to be a valuable tool in ensuring safe dam operation. Regular and systematic tracking of water levels, piezometric data, flow measurements, and geodetic surveys has allowed for early detection of changes and ensured that the dam's behaviour remains well understood.

Geophysical investigations are planned to be performed as a part of the monitoring program. As Tomova and Kisyov (2023) stated, implementing reliable monitoring systems is crucial for the early detection of potential stability issues. To determine the level of drainage and spatial distribution of water content, electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) is very useful to be performed. This geophysical technique can be deployed without disturbing the surface or subsurface infrastructure and can help identify zones of increased moisture content or water saturation (Tomova & Kisyov, 2024). The results would support the continued vertical expansion of the tailings dam in accordance with the master design plan. The dam's design enables phased elevation, while maintaining safety through consistent material quality, drainage management, and monitoring.

This approach reflects broader trends in sustainable mine waste management, where facilities are not only engineered for capacity and performance but also for adaptive monitoring, environmental compliance, and community safety. As emphasised by Yankova (2021), as global demand for mineral resources continues to rise, it becomes increasingly important for mining and mineral processing companies to adopt sustainable waste management practices. This includes not only minimising the environmental impact during operations, but also planning for effective reclamation of disturbed lands and ensuring long-term stewardship of rehabilitated ecosystems. The findings from 2022 reinforce the importance of maintaining strong data records, updating numerical models, and enhancing technical systems as the dam evolves.

Conclusions

This study assessed the structural stability and operational performance of the *Toranica* tailings dam using comprehensive monitoring data and geotechnical modeling from 2022. The results confirm that the dam system is operating within its design parameters and remains structurally and hydraulically stable. Both the upstream and downstream embankments showed no signs of deformation or instability, with pore pressures effectively controlled and seepage behavior consistent with safe operating conditions. The engineered drainage systems performed well, and no anomalies were detected in water levels, seepage discharge, or visual inspections.

The tailings pond water levels remained below critical thresholds, ensuring adequate freeboard and hydrological safety throughout the year. The technical monitoring program – comprising piezometric networks, geodetic benchmarks, flow measurements, and visual inspections – continues to provide valuable insights into the dam performance. Water discharged into the environment met applicable regulatory standards, confirming effective sedimentation and treatment systems. Numerical modelling validated these findings and demonstrated satisfactory factors of safety, supporting the continued operation and phased elevation of the dam in line with long-term planning.

To ensure continued safe operation and alignment with sustainability objectives, several recommendations are proposed. Routine monitoring should continue with enhanced

resolution and frequency, particularly during periods of dam raising or extreme weather. Geodetic surveying and piezometric control should be supported by geophysical methods, such as electrical resistivity tomography (ERT), which can help detect zones of increased water saturation, internal erosion, or structural heterogeneity within the dam body or foundation – especially in inaccessible or non-instrumented areas. Periodic ERT surveys can provide valuable complementary data to conventional instrumentation, improving the ability to detect early warning signs of seepage anomalies or instability.

Finally, sustainable mine waste management principles must remain central to all operational strategies. This includes protecting environmental quality, maintaining community safety, and ensuring long-term stewardship of tailings facilities through proactive monitoring, responsible engineering, and the integration of innovative technologies, such as ERT.

Acknowledgements

This research is in performance of Project BG05SFPR001-3.004-0002-C01 "Development and improvement of professional and interdisciplinary education in technical and economic sciences and enhancement of the research capacity of the extractive industry through project-based doctoral studies", funded by Programme "Education", co-funded by the European Union.

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